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Interview of Craig Atkinson, photographer and editor
May 12, 2020

About his work of editing and photography

How many zines and artist editions have you published since your beginning ?

About 750

Why publishing? Under what conditions was your structure created ?

I studied Fine Art for my degree and post grad degree, specialising in painting. The paintings took a long time, were big, heavy, expensive etc, so I could only really exhibit them in the UK, which I did. I never liked to exhibit the same work more than a couple of times though. Everything was time-luxurious and counter productive. I wanted an antidote to all of that, and to the gallery system, which seemed a closed and fairly elite network. I didn't see myself or my work fitting into that. Zines were right. Cheap, easily-postable, multiple, disposable, collectible...

How many novelties appear per year/month (on average) ? Do you have a maximum price to set for your editions, and if yes, why ?

About 70. They sell for around £6 — it's not a maximum as such, but I like them to be affordable, non-exclusive.

In what ways can we obtain your editions ?

Web, high st shops and galleries

Do you see an evolution in the themes you deal with ? Or do the same general themes recur regularly by being re-interpreted, and if so, why (is it an artistic desire to explore certain subjects as much as possible) ?

I publish British Documentary Photography. This is broad enough to cover many things. Some subjects I have published many times.

Do you see an evolution in aesthetics, the formal characteristics you choose? Do your editions follow some sort of guideline in terms of aesthetics?

The books are a series. Each has the same design.

Do you see an evolution in the techniques used? Do you adapt your techniques to the subjects or do you prefer to deepen certain techniques over time, and if so, why?

They're the same, as above.

About the photozine CRB :

What's with the photozine ?

Under what conditions was he born?

How does the principle work? (guest artists, themes, etc.)

How many copies is it printed?

How can the public get it?

What editorial aesthetic line was chosen and why?

See above

Are you a buyer and collector of artists' editions and zines? And if so, do you think that your collection influences, even unconsciously, your photographic work?

Not really a collector. There are things I like but I tend not to buy many books etc. I like pamphlets about things, not necessarily art or photography. I buy things more for their simplicity or design, but I buy them from flea markets and charity shops because they're no longer in print.

If you exhibit in fairs, do you see any differences in reception of the micro-edition, of themes, of audiences, of means according to the places and the organizing structures? Are there any very marked differences between the aesthetics of the artists' editions and the zines of each country? (for the countries you visited, and for the United Kingdom)

Not really. I think zines worldwide have a similar ethos and aesthetic. I think often people make zines for similar reasons, with similar methods and budgets.